

**EVALUATION OF BLOOD GLUCOSE RESPONSE OF LOCALLY CONSUMED
FOODS IN NORTH CENTRAL, NIGERIA.**

BY

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ABSTRACT

Glucose is a simple sugar and the human body's key energy source, providing about 3.75 kilocalories per gram. This study investigates the blood glucose responses to commonly consumed foods in North Central Nigeria, focusing on foods from Benue, Kogi, Nasarawa, and Niger states. Given the rising prevalence of metabolic disorders such as diabetes, understanding the glycemic impact of staple foods is critical. The aim of this study was to analyze the blood glucose responses elicited by selected local foods, providing necessary data for managing and preventing diabetes and other metabolic diseases. Meals were provided to the volunteers such as roasted yam, moi-moi, pounded yam with egusi soup, and others, with blood glucose levels measured at intervals of 0, 30, 60, 90, and 120 minutes using a glucometer. Materials included locally sourced foods, glucometer, kitchen utensils, lancets, cotton wool and hydrogen peroxide. The method also involved administering surveys to determine food consumption patterns, followed by blood glucose monitoring of participants. Statistical analysis using ANOVA evaluated the differences in glycemic responses among the foods. The results indicated that high-carbohydrate meals like pounded yam caused significant glucose spikes, while high-fiber foods like beans porridge resulted in more stable glucose levels, Fat-containing meals like roasted yam with red oil moderated glucose responses. In conclusion, These findings underscore the importance of incorporating low-glycemic foods into dietary recommendations to manage blood glucose levels and reduce the risk of diabetes. This data is essential for public health strategies aimed at improving diet and controlling diabetes in the region.